

CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN THE FAST FOOD RESTAURANTS: CASE OF GEN Z

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to investigate the relationship between service quality towards customer satisfaction and customer loyalty related to fast food services. Fast food services expanded exponentially when the number of service providers increased year by year. Data collection was done through questionnaires distributed in selected fast-food restaurants. Three hundred forms distributed, but only 236 usable responses received for final analysis. The results indicate that service quality influences customer satisfaction as well as customer loyalty. It was also reported that customer satisfaction partially mediates between service quality towards customer loyalty. The results are significant to the service providers in deciding on their operations and marketing strategy.

KEYWORDS: Customer loyalty, Service quality, Customer satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Fast food restaurant is among a great business to be venture at with the current population and generations. The majority of current populations are from Gen Y and Gen 4, ranging from 24 to 43 years old. They hold the most reliable purchasing power and dominant in the service-based industry, fast food. Previous generations of baby boomers and Gen X could be skeptical about taking too much fast food as they grew up with the high discipline and home-based food culture. The generations claimed that eating fast food is not recommended for dietary [1], [2]. The fact is that generation's change, and the same goes for customer behavior and purchase intentions. Fast food is no longer associate with obesity [3].

In Brunei, there is not less than 20 type of fast-food restaurants all over the country. The competition among the restaurants can be considered as harsh compared with the potential market share to be earned. The customer, at the same time, is very knowledgeable. They know which restaurants serve the best food that value to them. They used to review, read comments, share experiences over social media. Such a situation forced the service provider to be more alert on their market needs, wants, and demands.

Understanding the needs of the potential customer is essential as service providers need customers in order to survive. The advantage of customers is that they have more choices and options. They may choose the one that suitable for them. Failing in meeting their needs will end up failing or reduce in slow market growth. To grow, the service provider must first ensure that they understand how to satisfy their customer and eventually lead them to be loyal. This study will have focused on the factors that lead to customer loyalty with customer satisfaction as the mediator between service quality and customer loyalty.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Customer loyalty

Doing business in the 21st century faced a tough challenge in meeting customer needs and wants. The type of customer is different from a few decades ago. Today's customer is complicated and highly demanded[4]. They have access to information and know what they want. The advanced technology supported by the internet has given the customer access to select and compare the best service providers that they think may fulfill their needs[5]. Customers have access to compare and read past customer reviews and learn from their experiences. Such a situation is a challenge to the service provider in meeting customer needs and wants and competing among the other service providers. One of the way solution that may keep service providers at a steady competing level is via having a loyal customer[6].

Loyal by definition, according to [7], is the strength level of a relationship between customer and service providers. The more durable it is, the more loyal is the customer[8]. Past research stated that loyal customers are a good investment in gaining profit over the long term but can help service providers gain more customers should the service provider manage it properly. It was also highlighted by [9]–[11] that loyal is representing the customer commitment and faithful towards the service providers. It is also mentioned by [12] that loyal

customer tends to revisit or repurchase from the same service providers. Loyal customers, in other words, will keep on supporting the service provider because of their strong relationship[13].

Past research also highlighted that service providers need to think of the best possible actions to benefit from loyal customers[14]. A loyal customer will always have a positive perception that their service providers are the best compared to others. The loyal customer believed that the service provider offered them the best value that meets their expectations[15]. A loyal customer has good faith in the service provider, and they believed that they had made the right choice. As a result, loyal customers will not quickly churn or attract the offering from competitors [16]. That kind of commitment indirectly leads to the sustainability and survival of the service providers in the industry.

Customer loyalty according to past research [17]–[19] can be divided into three categories that service providers may focus in achieving it. There is a type of loyalty based on emotional[8]. This type of loyalty derived from the emotional connections from the customer and the service providers. For example, in fast-food restaurants, the restaurants managed to create a suitable atmosphere or ambiance that matched the customer needs. Customers were hooked by their psychological commitment based on the services offered. Customers could enjoy family environments or have a good memory of the decoration based on the restaurant's[20]. There could be many possible items or factors that may increase the emotional relations between the customer and the service provider. Besides that [8] reported that customers could also become loyal to rational. The objective type of customer loyalty is usually based on the eternal reward offered by the service provider. The more you come to the restaurants, the more points you earned and gain. Reward concept according to [11] could be in terms of amount spent or visitation; customers could gain points that they can use back for their benefits from the range of services offered by the restaurant[19].

There is also another type of loyalty based on transactional[7], [21]. Customers will typically repeat purchases once they are attached to the restaurant, for example. A customer will have repeated the purchase once their experience with the restaurant is positive and memorable. It could be because of the special menu or unique services that made the customer decide to return for a repeat purchase. The service provider needs to offer a standard quality service to all customers to maintain and meet customer expectations[7].

There are many benefits of having customer loyalty in service provider databases. Loyal customers will save marketing costs since they are not only coming for repeated times but also helping the service provider attract more customers [22], [23]. The loyal customer tends to recommend and suggest the service providers to their family and friends. They will also share their positive experiences for others to know and aware of. Loyal customers also according to [14], [15], [24] will involve in cross-selling and upselling of the service provider products. They tend to explore the other types of products available from the service providers.

Besides that, a loyal customer is easy to approach and get feedback. A loyal customer will share their comment and feedback to the service providers for their actions and attention[18]. They spoke from the customers' perspective; thus, the service provider needs to pay attention and take necessary actions. The past researcher also mentioned that loyal customers would spend more than other customers[15]. However, the percentages quoted differ from one to another researcher, but it is between 18 to 25% higher. Besides, that service provider can have a good and almost accurate sales forecast based on records. The sales forecast in marketing is essential as the service providers may need to prepare and ready to maintain the service level to customers[25].

It is recommended by many researchers[8], [20], [26] that service provider increase their effort to manage the loyal customer as the loyal customer brings excellent impacts not only in terms of revenue, profit but the brand image[27]. The loyal customer will promote the best services about the restaurant, the quality of their food and services, and the unique about the places to be shared by others. Such positive recommendations and testimonials bring a positive image to the service providers[9].

Service providers in the first place must aware and know what the determinants or factors that can prosper customers towards loyalty[10] are. Understanding the factors may provide service providers a valuable knowledge to be used in their long term marketing strategy.

2.2 Customer satisfaction

Scholars argued whether customers could achieve the loyalty stage without going through the satisfaction level. Some debates went around, but most of the literature claimed that customers must be satisfied before gaining the loyalty level. However, there is research made [28]–[30] that claimed customer satisfaction might not lead to customer loyalty. It means that a service provider cannot sit back once they have scored the service level

satisfying customers [28]. More things to do as a competitor will not just let the service providers earn their portion of possible market share. Satisfaction can be the mediator or control variables between the factors that lead to customer loyalty[29]. Customer satisfaction is the overall customer experience based on their expectations and service delivered. It means that customers will get satisfied should the service provider managed to offer something that is meeting or exceeding customer expectations [31]. At the same time, a customer may get dissatisfied should the service provider failed to meet their expectations.

Service satisfaction is always associated with the theory of disconfirmation theory. Customers will get satisfied once they gain more. Marketers used the theory in understanding customer behavior and effort made in trying to understand the actual customer needs and wants. The service provider that managed to satisfied their customer will have enjoyed more significant benefits that may bring to advantage in terms of operation and competition[32]. Customer satisfaction at the same time can be considered as a critical differentiator between one service provider to another[33]. Customer satisfaction has become one of the critical elements or goals of service-based organizations[32]. Past research [34], [35] indicates that a satisfied customer is willing to insensitive towards the price. Some increase in price will not make satisfied customer change their mind by changing to another service provider.

Research conducted since many decades ago only focused on either satisfied or dissatisfied. It means that service providers may or may not have options in the service delivery towards satisfying customers [31]. The cost of a dissatisfied customer is high. Customers will tell and share their experiences with many others, especially their family and friends. The cost of weak or low-level delivery will indirectly bring a negative impact on service providers[36]. By acknowledging that, the service provider must carefully understand their customer needs and design something related to products, people, or processes[37].

The challenges faced by the service provider are to understand and know precisely what the customer expects? Is it the courtesy or knowledge? Is it the timeliness or quality? Alternatively, simply make it the overall experience. Customers can know whether the service provider is focusing on customers or not by looking at their vision and mission. Almost every service-based business organization will put priority on their customer. They change their operation and culture from product-oriented to market-driven or market-oriented. Such a thing is part of their efforts to meet and win customer hearts towards overall satisfaction[30], [38].

Customer satisfaction is essential because it is the first step in linking the customer towards loyalty. Many statistics based on past research claimed that customer satisfaction leads to positive positioning of the service providers. It was claimed that satisfied customers are 80% more likely to return for a revisit[30]. It is also claimed that 90% of customers who dissatisfied will decide not to come back for a second visit[39]. Ironically, both are equally important to service providers. The questions that almost lead to further studied were whether the satisfaction would lead to loyalty or not. The same issues were highlighted in this study, where customer satisfaction acts as a mediator. Whether the role of the factors towards customer loyalty is higher, or they need customer satisfaction to mediate towards the loyalty level.

Service providers were recommended to keep track of their service level continuously by asking feedback from customers. The communication, whether verbally or questionnaire-based, may provide some insightful information from the customer's opinion. The service provider needs to take action and find solutions on the comment or complaint from customers. The service provider that managed to satisfied customers is reported [40]–[42] will also satisfy their staff or employee. It was also reported [42], [43] that happy employees lead happy customers. A satisfied and happy employee will help the service provider to serve the customer better. They are aware of the importance of the customer to them and the organization. Such understanding is critical in order to keep the business runs well, increase productivity and quality.

Past research indicates that there are quite several factors that satisfied customers. Overall, customer satisfaction may be derived from many elements, such as friendly employees or helpful employees[44]. Both are representing the role of the employee towards customer satisfaction. It can be associate with the level of customer interactions with employees. Among other factors are quick services, accurate billing, and value. It involves many elements that may influence customers towards satisfaction, but the fact is that service providers must know what customers expect and how they communicate with customers[43]. Very often that service providers make a false claim in their advertisements that lead to high expectations from customers. However, the service provider must also not have been involved in underpromised by keeping their profile low and taken advantage of by the competitor[42]. The bottom line is that positive communication with good unique selling points and differentiation that can be offered to customers should be prioritized in sales[45]. Service providers must find a way what areas that they are right and do best compared to the rest in the market[46]. Matching both the service provider's uniqueness and customer needs will eventually lead to positive customer experiences and satisfaction[47].

2.3 Service quality

An interesting statement quoted by [48] is “perceptions result from a combination of (a) expectations of both what will and what should happen and (b) the reality of the service encounter. The lower the expectation of what should happen, the higher the perception of what did happen, and the higher the expectation of what would happen, the higher the perception of what did happen”. Service quality is basically about the difference between what customers expect and what is received or experienced[49]. It is about the gap between the overall services that the customer thinks they should get compared to what has been provided. The gap determined whether service quality is positive or negative[50].

Service-based, like fast-food restaurants, need to focus more on service quality. Customers today not only concerns about the service quality but to the extent of food quality. The initial service quality G.A.P. model was introduced by [51] with a basis of five dimensions, namely reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy, and responses. Earlier than that, a service quality model based on technical quality, functional quality, and the corporate image was introduced by Grönroos (1984). Since then, the service quality model experienced some phases of changes in terms of additional dimensions and approaches.

One thing that never changes is the demand from the customer towards the high service quality. Over the years, service providers experienced a change in patterns and trends in customer behaviors. Customer nowadays is sophisticated and impatient [48]. It was stated that customer would switch to a competitor should the service provider fail to provide the services as per the customer expectations [53]

Among the crucial factors observed by customers, customers are the ability of the employee to perform their tasks as promised. The service provider should have focused on the deliverable as per their promises to customers dependably and accurately[49]. Such things include the response time taken from the moment the customer orders the counter until the time is taken for the food to be ready. It also includes the accuracy of the foods based on the order. The service provider must ensure that the staff's service can be dependable and reliable[50].

It is also essential for the restaurants to look into assurance matters such as the knowledge of the products. Customers may need some explanation, and such questions may need to be response accordingly[49]. It should reply courteously that, at the same time, it will represent the confidence of the employee. The service provider must ensure that all employees have undergone enough training in terms of the process and the product's knowledge. Research also indicates that employees need to be responsive enough to service customers. It means that employees must be able and willing to help customers by providing prompt services[50]. The combination of willingness and prompt services could score a high level of satisfaction from customers' view.

Brunei is only 5,765 km², with the population less than 500,000. The limited geographical areas, however, not limited to a large number of competitors. Service providers need to select the best location with full services of facilities that may ease customers to come and dine in. External facilities include such as parking space and access to the restaurants. It also includes using the latest equipment that may produce a better quality of food based on technology and, finally, the staff[54]. The appearance must be neat and uniform to present the high image of the service providers' branding. Whether there is a need for the staff to wear uniforms depends on the customer[55]. The results from past research found that the appearance of employees could depend on the nature of works. In this sense, the customer seems to be more practical in terms of their perceptions.

The last factors of service quality based on [48], [53] is empathy. Service providers need to ensure that the selected staff is among those who have the essential motivation to help others. Restaurants required an employee that can serve customer individualized instead of a custom approach[56]. A recent report indicates that the customer went to the restaurant for purposes. Some may come for food style, value for money, locations, and perhaps experiences[57]. Each customer may come with various intentions. Employees need to understand the customer and serve them accordingly.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research aims to measure the relationship between service loyalty, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. This research employed a quantitative method where data are collected using survey forms. There are altogether 21 questions asked in the questionnaires split into four sections. Respondents may take 3-4 minutes to complete the questionnaire. 300 was targeted for the data collection; however, the final usable data collected is just 236. Questionnaires were distributed in selected fast food restaurants with the permission of the management. 5 point Likert scale was used to provide convenient for respondents to answer the questions. Data were analyzed using AMOS.

IV. RESULTS

In this study, discriminant validity was also assessed. According to Hair et al. (2010), the square root of the AVE value for each structure should be larger than the shared relationship coefficients to establish the discriminant validity of the factors in the model. AVE for all constructs is within the range of 0.88 to 0.92, while C.R. is within the scope of 0.89 to 0.93. All results indicate positive and within the minimum acceptable values.

Table 1: Overall reliability of the constructs and factors loadings of indications

Items	Factor loading	t-value	MSV	ASV	AVE	CR
Service Quality						
ServQ1	0.96	23.50	0.78	0.65	0.90	0.91
ServQ2	0.98	24.24				
ServQ3	0.91	22.49				
ServQ4	0.86	19.32				
ServQ5	0.83	17.24				
Customer satisfaction						
CSat1	0.93	21.31	0.82	0.67	0.86	0.89
CSat2	0.94	22.11				
CSat3	0.91	21.56				
CSat4	0.82	18.24				
CSat5	0.81	18.14				
Customer loyalty						
Cloy 1	0.92	21.17	0.71	0.62	0.78	0.81
Cloy 2	0.93	21.10				
Cloy 3	0.82	18.35				
Cloy 4	0.76	16.18				

Table 2 confirmed the discriminant validity. These results also demonstrated that all measures were reliable (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988). Means, standard deviations, and correlations of latent variables are presented in Table 2. The results in Table 2 indicate that all relationships are significant.

Table 2: Means, standard deviations and correlations of study constructs

	Mean	SD	Service Quality	Customer satisfaction	Customer loyalty
Service Quality	4.25	0.75	(0.93)		
Customer satisfaction	4.00	0.80	0.87	(0.91)	
Customer loyalty	4.50	0.79	0.71	0.78	(0.88)

Table 3: Path estimates of structural models

Hypothesis		Standardized path coefficients	t-values	Result
H1	Service quality → Customer satisfaction	0.25	5.34	Supported
H2	Service quality → Customer loyalty	0.23	5.66	Supported
H3	Customer satisfaction → Customer loyalty	0.26	5.23	Supported

In the present study, the hypotheses were tested using structural equation modeling. Therefore, the fit indices values of the appropriate model and path estimates are shown in Table 3. Service quality influences customer satisfaction positively ($\beta = 0.25$ $p < 0.001$), supporting H1. Further, service quality positively influences customer loyalty ($\beta = 0.23$ $p < 0.001$), thereby supporting H2. At the same time, customer satisfaction was found to positively influence customer loyalty ($\beta = 0.26$ $p < 0.001$); therefore, H3 is accepted.

Table 4: Path estimates of structural models

Standardized path coefficients value				
	Full mediation model		Partial mediation model	
	β	t-value	β	t-value
Service quality → Customer loyalty			0.23	5.68
Service quality → Customer satisfaction	0.62	10.42	0.25	5.35
Customer satisfaction → Customer loyalty	0.72	14.73	0.26	5.25

According to partial mediation model, service quality towards customer satisfaction ($\beta = 0.25$ $p < 0.001$) and customer satisfaction predicted customer loyalty ($\beta = 0.26$ $p < 0.001$). These results show that although the indirect effect of attention to a customer on customer loyalty through mediation was ($\beta = 0.25 \times 0.26 = 0.065$ $p < 0.001$), the direct effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty was 0.72. The indirect effect is weaker than the direct effect. Therefore, partially supported. According to the partial mediation model (see Table 4),

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results indicate that service quality positively supported customer satisfaction as well as customer loyalty. This means that service quality is one of the essential elements that must be offered in fast-food restaurants to meet customer expectations and, hence, lead to customer satisfaction. At the same time, satisfied customers with a standard enjoyment and benefits offered by the restaurants will turn to be loyal. The results support past researches related to service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty [58], [59]

It was also noticed that customer satisfaction is partially supported by customer loyalty. Such situations could be due to fierce competition among the industry market players'. Fast food restaurants currently practice high service quality procedures, so there is less differentiation between one brand and another. At the same time, customers have more bargaining power, and they have the power to choose what to consume. The fierce competition among the fast-food industry has resulted in high service quality, and more focused on customer satisfaction.

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